

An Analysis of Internet Security Challenges Faced By Organisations in Botswana: *The Reviewed Literature*

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper was to analyse internet security challenges faced by organisations in Botswana. The paper used the Qualitative Content Analysis approach to analyse secondary data from published articles, conference papers, news articles and government publications that provided statistical data about internet security issues that have been reported by organisations in Botswana and other countries. This paper recommended solutions to internet security challenges faced by organisations as follows: Ensuring that all computers are installed with genuine antivirus software; Regular antivirus updates; Ensuring that firewalls are properly configured to block viruses and intrusions; Filtering email traffic; Regular computer scans; regular data backups; Monitoring system logs; Educating users about security issues; Hiring qualified security experts, as well as implementing information security policies. Most importantly organisations should have sustainable financial budgets towards securing their systems.

Keywords: Cyber Crime; Network Security, Cyber Security, Internet Security Challenges; Security Attacks; Security Threats; Security Solutions; Security Mechanisms; Computer Security

Introduction

Businesses and government departments in Botswana are worryingly alarmed by securing their physical and information assets due to cyber-attacks; the rise of internet usage in organisations has given opportunities for hackers to explore their hacking skills on cybercrime activities (AllAfrica, 2019). A report by Symantec Corporation (2016) indicated that spam incidents originating from Africa accounted for the largest number of security breaches. There were 1.1 billion spam events observed by Symantec that originated from Africa, representing 3.5% of the global total. Because of these incidents, it is evident that organisations have fallen victims of cyber-attacks because of the global threats imposed on their network systems and data (The Patriot, 2016). In his article titled "Computer security – Threats & Solutions", Honan (2014) pointed out that, cybercrime has become a business from which cyber criminals are looking to steal valuable information from organisations. He emphasized that cybercrime is becoming sophisticated by day as the increase in network usage by organisations becomes more sophisticated and inevitable (Honan, 2014).

Network security is increasingly becoming a very important subject in computing, as a result, the exponential rate at which dark world software developers introduce sophisticated hacking tools used to intrude systems, is probably one of the factors leading to a rise in computer security crimes (Yan, Yu, Gong & Li, 2016). In a report produced by Identity Theft Resource Center (2020), it was revealed that from January 1, 2005 to January 31, 2020 there were a total of 11,365 internet breaches and the number of confidential records that were exposed as a result of these attacks rose to 1,660,423,788.

Therefore, this paper was set out to analyze internet security challenges faced by organisations in Botswana and uses the terms network security, cyber security and computer security interchangeable to refer to internet security.

Problem statement

The rate of cyber-attacks in Botswana has been reported at an alarming rate which led to Botswana been labeled the hardest hit country by cybercrimes in Africa (The Patriot, 2016). According to an article written by Mbazo (2019), it was indicated that 143 cybercrime cases were reported by Botswana law enforcement agencies. According to the report, cybercrime incidents had increased since the year 2015 to the year 2018. These

statistics indicate that Botswana is under the spot light of cyber criminals influenced by lack of robust security resources and skilled manpower (Kaimb, 2018).

Botswana just like any other African countries, is still growing in technology and numbers of experienced and qualified security experts are low as evidenced by the African Cyber Security report (2018). According to Mbazo (2019), the number of certified experts in digital forensics in Botswana was said to be at 30, which is a very low number in the country when compared to industry needs (Kaimb, 2018). Because of this lack of expertise, organisations suffer from cyber-attacks as their systems are not secured at least by experts in the field.

Owing to these shortcomings and little research done in this area, this paper analyzed the challenges faced by organisations in Botswana so as to establish solutions to internet security issues.

Objectives of the study

This paper was driven by the following objectives;

- 1) To determine the challenges faced by organisations as a result of internet security attacks.
- 2) To determine the types of internet security attacks that have been reported by organisations.
- 3) To determine the security measures which organisations should implement in order to improve the security of their systems.

Research questions

This study addressed the following research questions;

- 1) What are the challenges faced by organisations as a result of internet security attacks?
- 2) What type of internet security attacks and threats have been reported by organisations?
- 3) What are security measures that organisations should implement in order to improve the security of their systems?

Significance of the study

Findings of this study provide relevant data and information that would ultimately help organisations to implement robust internet security measures. These findings will also help organisations to create security awareness amongst their employees in order to improve their security awareness when using computer systems on a daily basis. These findings would also be used by security experts towards formulating information security policies and frameworks that seek to address key and pertinent security issues that are critical to business continuity more especially in Botswana. The paper also outlined critical security measures that serve as a checklist for organisations and internet users to take heed of when they use the internet so as to prevent cyber-attacks and internet security setbacks.

Literature review

Introduction

What is internet security? According to Fruhlinger (2019) internet security is defined as measures that are put in place for protecting computer systems and data during their transmission over the internet. Internet security is also known as cyber security (kaspersky, nd). The primary goal of internet security is to protect information and or data against unauthorized access (Fruhlinger, 2019).

Internet security deals with the protection of information technology assets that are accessible via computer networks (Frizell, 2018). It entails mechanisms which provide security services for data communication and storage. Network security aims to ensure that the entire network within an organization is secure in order to improve the usability, reliability, integrity, and safety of networks and data (Yan, et al., 2016).

According to Rhee (2003), the principal objectives of securing networks are to guarantee the Confidentiality, Integrity, and Availability of data and information. These three pillars of Network Security are often represented as the CIA triangle. These concepts are further elaborated as follows:

- **Confidentiality:** The purpose of confidentiality is to protect information and data from unauthorized access. Confidentiality ensures that data is available only to authorized users (Rhee, 2003).
- **Integrity:** This deals with maintaining and assuring the accuracy and consistency of data in order to promote the reliability and integrity of information and data (Rhee, 2003).
- **Availability:** The function of availability is to ensure that information and data, network resources, and services are continuously available whenever they are requested by legitimate users (Rhee, 2003).

Internet security challenges faced by organisations

Cybercrime is not only a matter of attacks against the confidentiality, integrity and availability of computer data and systems but against the core values and the human development potential of societies increasingly relying on information technology. In light of this, governments cannot remain passive in addressing these issues; governments have the obligation to protect their societies and individuals against cybercrimes.

According to IEEE.ORG (2017) and Mann (2017) several industries were subjected to attacks on IOT devices. Research shows that 29% of transportation organisations had been subjected to cyber-attacks, followed by 22% from the energy, oil and gas industry. The infrastructure maintained by these industries is critical, thus organisations cannot ignore the importance of putting trained personnel and advanced security systems in place in order to protect their assets (IEEE.ORG, 2017; Mann, 2017).

Another reported challenge faced by organisations is that a few countries have legal cybercrime frameworks in place (Kshetri, 2019). Reports show that at least 11 countries in the continent had specific laws and provisions in place to deal with cybercrimes and electronic evidence: Botswana, Cameroon, Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Mauritania, Mauritius, Nigeria, Senegal, Tanzania, Uganda and Zambia are some of the examples (Kshetri, 2019). However, reports show that in other African countries, the implementation of these legal frameworks is still lagging behind, most probably due to limited capacities of law enforcement, prosecutors and limited expertise in the field of cybercrime, thereby leading to an impediment to an effective criminal justice response system to curb cybercrimes and other related offences (Symantec Corporation, 2016).

The Data Breach Investigation Report by Phonsa & Arazi (2016) based on real-world investigations reported over 100,000 security incidents. The report examined trends across different industry verticals such as finance, retail, information technology and others and indicated that attacks on web applications accounted for 8% of overall reported incidents in the reporting period of 2016. In total, the report showed that attacks on web applications accounted for over 40 % of incidents which resulted in data breaches.

Therefore, international cybercrime laws are needed. These laws should stipulate the investigation processes, prosecution and adjudication of offences against cybercrimes and or any crime committed by means of computer systems. Cyber laws should also outline the procedure for securing electronic evidence in relation to any crime for presentation before the courts. Most importantly, the adoption and implementation of these laws requires mutual international cooperation amongst nations given the transnational nature of cybercrimes (IEEE.ORG, 2017; Mann, 2017).

Types of security attacks and threats reported by organisations

There are many identified and classified potential threats to network security that have been reported by organisations in Botswana (Kaimb, 2018). In most cases, these threats tempter with the confidentiality, integrity and availability of data in organisations. The most commonly reported attacks are conducted through spams that come as email attachments (Kaimb, 2018). The security threats are further discussed in more detail as follows;

Prince (2009) in his article entitled "Top 9 IT Threats and Solutions", identified top 9 security threats to computer networks similar to those reported in Botswana and also provided solutions to each threat he described. These include;

Threat 1: Malicious insider: He identifies employees with malicious intentions as the biggest threat that most organisations are faced with and also emphasizes that employees should be offered training on internet

security in order to raise their awareness on computer security and its significance in the organization (Prince, 2009).

Threat 2: Malware: the author cites that websites are the most common platforms in which viruses and worms are spread. To remedy this, the author emphasized that URLs should be filtered and antivirus software should be deployed to guard against malware (Prince, 2009).

Threat 3: Exploited vulnerabilities: the author described hackers as the biggest threat as they use sophisticated techniques to detect weaknesses in systems and software in order to exploit them. He highlights that organisations should invest in patch management solutions that offer full visibility into networks in order to protect operating systems. He also identified host-based intrusion prevention (HIPS) as another mechanism to be employed for monitoring systems anomaly behaviour (Prince, 2009).

Threat 4: Social engineering: the author identified telephones, mobile phones, text messaging as some of the methods in which hackers get information from staff. He advised that staff should be offered training on social engineering so as to increase their resilience (Prince, 2009).

Threat 5: Careless Employees: the author explained that careless employees can pose security threats to the organisations systems due to lack of following right processes and procedures. Such employees should be offered training for raising their awareness on security (Prince, 2009).

Threat 6: Reduced budgets: the author described reduced budgets as other means that could lead to compromise in security. With low budgets, organisations usually fail to pay for software updates and also fail to upgrade their security systems. He advised that organisations should consider opting for software- as -a -service (saas) solutions so as to cut costs and also choose service providers that offer a wide range of services (Prince, 2009).

Threat 7: Remote workers: the author also pointed out that organisations should use the same systems for telecommuters both for onsite and offsite workers (Prince, 2009).

Threat 8: Unstable 3rd party providers; the author advised that organisations should avoid working with providers that cannot sustain themselves in the market but should go for providers that have been in business for long and have been stable for years. Choosing a provider that offers multiple solutions can reduce the burden on existing IT resources (Prince, 2009).

Threat 9: Open source software; the author identified open source software as sources of security threats and that organisations should deny users from using unlicensed software (Prince, 2009).

Internet security mechanisms for improving internet security

This paper identified the use and implementation of Access Controls, Encipherment and Digital Signatures as some of the robust mechanisms which organisations should consider using in improving the security of their systems. These concepts are further discussed as follows;

1) Using Access Controls For Improving Internet Security

This mechanism is used to provide access control services which use identification and authentication methods to determine and enforce the access rights of the entity (Rhee, 2003; Ellis & Speed, 2003). In IT Disaster Recovery, developing a secure network entails the implementation of robust controls, software and hardware rules and processes that are enforced in order to reduce or mitigate issues of network security (Rhee, 2003). Controls are divided into three categories such as: Preventive Controls, Detective Controls and Corrective Controls. Each of these controls is further discussed as follows;

- **Preventive controls:** These are implemented to stop users from performing any act that is detrimental to assets of an organisation assets. Preventive measures are meant to serve as barriers that require the use of usernames and passwords for accessing information or systems (Rhee, 2003; Ellis & Speed, 2003).
- **Detective controls:** These are implemented to detect any event or act that is suspicious to organisations' systems; these activities are recorded in the computer event log. Software that does this task sends an alarming message to administrators so that they can act to the intrusion (Rhee, 2003).

- **Corrective controls:** These are implemented to correct any event that could have caused an intrusion to a computer system. These controls are employed for disaster recovery and should be clearly outlined in the Business Continuity Plan document.

These controls are employed with the aim to prevent, detect and correct any defect that could happen to an organization caused by internet security threats and breaches. Most importantly, controls must be reviewed and tested in order to determine if they are effective on a daily basis (Rhee, 2003). In addition to the controls discussed here, it is always advisable for organisations to also develop risk assessment plans in order to secure networks. The risk assessment process entails the identification of possible threats, the nature of threats, actors and responses to such threats or intrusions.

Implementation of Wi-Fi version 3

Research indicates that the implementation of Wi-Fi Protected Access 3 (WPA3) improves internet security. WPA3 represents the latest generation in mainstream security for wireless networks (Rhee, 2003). It improves the level of security from WPA2 standard which was released in 2004. WPA3 comes in three main forms which include the following:

- **WPA3 Personal (WPA-3 SAE) Mode:** is designed for personal Wi-Fi networks and is intended to offer protection against password-guessing attacks while also being more resilient. (Rhee, 2003).
- **WPA3 Enterprise Mode:** is designed to better protect sensitive data transmission over enterprise networks (Rhee, 2003).
- **Wi-Fi Enhanced Open Mode:** is designed for public networks based on opportunistic wireless encryption (OWE). It provides encryption and privacy on **open**, non-password-protected networks in areas such as shopping malls and hotels (Rhee, 2003).

Use of Virtual private network connections

A VPN network extends the functionality of a private network and allows secure exchange of information across public networks. This gives users the sense that their devices are connected to the same network. VPN allows for secure access of local area networks of an organization from various geographical areas thus allowing organisations to make connections to different branches in a secured manner. VPNs are established through a point to point connection through techniques such as traffic encryption and tunneling protocols. In essence VPNs supports the implementation of wide area networks (Rhee, 2003; Ellis & Speed, 2003).

Implementation of Firewalls

A firewall is a security mechanism that serves as a barrier through which all internet connections are filtered; it operates as a filtering tool of internet protocol addresses (IP) and media access control (MAC) addresses of traffic from computers requesting access to a computer network (Rhee, 2003; Ellis & Speed, 2003). A firewall is implemented between the internet and the premises network so as to control links from inside and outside the network, in a way to deny unauthorized access. According to Rhee (2003) and Ellis et al, (2003), firewalls use four core techniques to control network access, and these include;

- **Service control:** This means that the firewall filters IP addresses to determine the type of services to be granted to the machine needing access.
- **Direction control:** This allows for the directed follow of services via configured firewall ports to reach the client requesting a service.
- **User Control:** This entails the use of passwords and usernames, with regard to permissions of the user, and what they are configured to access. Services are availed to the user according to access rights.
- **Behavior control:** This controls the manner in which services are utilized with the objective of eliminating unusual patterns.

Deployment of Routers

According to Rhee (2003) routers connect computers to the internet for secured transmission of data packets between computers and networks. The router enforces security through the use of IP addresses so as to

determine the destination of data packets. Routers offer the following security features: guest network access, built-in firewall, enhanced parental controls, time-based access restrictions and VPN connections at the router level.

Deployment of Network switches

Switches are used to connect devices on a single network towards enforcing security. Switches use media access control (MAC) addresses to forward data to relevant destinations through a technique called packet switching for receiving and pushing data; switches are layer 2 devices in the OSI model (Rhee, 2003).

Network intrusion protection systems

This comprises of hardware and software systems that are employed to enforce network security from attackers. Network intrusion protection systems comprise of firewalls, sniffers and antivirus software that block unauthorized access (Rhee, 2003).

Deployment of Secure Web Gateways

This security feature blocks traffic from entering a local network of an organisation. It serves to protect users from malicious attacks from websites and emails. It also enforces the implementation and compliance to regulatory policies of an organisation (Rhee, 2003). Having developed and identified various security mechanisms for achieving network security, it is essential for organisations to determine and decide where they would apply them for effective implementation of security.

2) Using Encipherment For Improving Internet Security

This mechanism provides data confidentiality services by transforming data into non-readable formats. It uses encryption-decryption algorithms which use secret keys (Rhee, 2003). This section introduces the contemporary encryption methods which include symmetric cryptography and asymmetric cryptography. The components of a cryptosystem include (Rhee, 2003);

- Plain text: text that must be protected throughout the communication
- Encryption algorithm; a mechanism that converts plain text into cipher text
- Cipher text; non readable text after conversion
- Decryption algorithm: a mechanism that converts cipher text back to its readable format which is plain text
- Encryption / Decryption key; a secret value unique and known only to the sender that is used to identify the plain text

Symmetric Cryptography

This algorithm uses a single key for encryption and decryption of information. It employs methods like Digital Encryption Standard, IDEA and Triple –DES. Figure 1 shows how the process of the symmetric mechanism works (Rhee, 2003).

Figure 1: (Symmetric Cryptography)

Diagram created in Microsoft Visio, and adopted from Gigatux(online)

Asymmetric Cryptography

This type of algorithm uses different keys for encrypting and decrypting the same piece of information (Rhee, 2003). These sets of keys are known as public keys and private keys as depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Asymmetric Cryptography

(Diagram created in Microsoft Visio, and adopted from Gigatux(online))

3) Using Digital Signatures For Improving Internet Security

This mechanism is the electronic equivalence of ordinary signatures in electronic information which provides authenticity to data (Rhee, 2003). Digital signatures include the use of encryption algorithms such as follows;

- ✓ **Rivest–Shamir–Adleman (RSA):** This algorithm uses a public key to encrypt data bands and a private key to decrypt data. It is mostly used to encrypt sensitive data broadcasted over unsecure channels like the internet (Rhee, 2003).
- ✓ **Advanced Encryption Standard (AES):** This algorithm consists of three kinds of ciphers including 128 bits, 192 bits and 256 bits. This algorithm provides robust security features and uses symmetric cryptography, where a single key is used to encrypt and decrypt data (Rhee, 2003).
- ✓ **Message-Digest Algorithm (MD5):** This algorithm uses 128 bits where data integrity is verified by variable length processing, to output a fixed variable length (Rhee, 2003).
- ✓ **Blowfish:** This is a symmetric algorithm that uses 64 bit block size and 32 to 448 bits of key length (Rhee, 2003).

- ✓ **Data Encryption Standard (DES):** These algorithms consist of 64 bit block ciphers and 54 bit of key sizes: the algorithm encrypts data in three ways using distinct keys (Rhee, 2003).

In summary, reviewed literature provided more insight and information about the core internet security challenges faced by organisations. Literature also pointed out ways in which network security could be achieved. The role that networks play in organisations' communication and storage strategies has been pointed out. The importance and necessity for internet security in organisations was also explored as a means to achieve the findings of this study.

Methodology

This paper used qualitative content analysis approach. Content analysis is a systematic technique used to analyze the informational contents of textual data in order to design themes (Mayring, 2000). This paper analysed secondary data from published articles, conference papers, news articles and government publications that provided statistical data about internet security issues that have been reported by organisations in Botswana and other countries. According to Johnston (2013) secondary data collection begins with an investigation with the objective to learn what is already known about a topic through reviewing secondary sources and investigations on what other researchers have already conducted in the specified area of interest. This paper therefore applied the systematic content analysis approach and analyzed internet security challenges faced by organisations in Botswana with the aim of establishing internet security solutions.

Findings and discussion

Findings from reviewed literature indicate that computer networks are valued resources by almost all businesses and government departments. These resources enable organisations to share resources, streamline business processes, collaborate within departments as well as improve customer service (Frizell, 2018). Amid all the benefits presented by the internet, the threats on networks have significantly increased due to advancement in technology. Findings reveal that the use of internet for various online business transactions continues to present challenges of information theft and other attacks on information systems.

Findings also identified the different types of threats that have been reported by organisations in Botswana (Kaimb, 2018) and other affected countries. Some of these threats include: malware, phishing, man-in-the-middle attack, denial-of-service attack, malicious insider, exploited vulnerabilities, social engineering, careless employees, reduced budgets, remote workers, unstable 3rd party providers, as well as open source software (Prince, 2009; kaspersky, nd).

Findings also discovered the need for organisations to implement cryptography and access controls in order to enforce internet security at all levels (Rhee, 2003). Many solutions have been provided for organisations and internet users to implement (Kaimb, 2018). In addition, it is worth noting that the ultimate goal of securing information technology assets is for business continuity (Kshetri, 2015). Therefore, it is crucial that organisations should have business continuity plans that integrate with security policies and ICT strategic plans with an eye to ensure that businesses are able to function amid disasters presented by cybercrimes and internet security breaches.

In this respect, the business continuity plan (BCP) document should detail procedures that clearly outline what needs to be done in case there is a disaster. The plan should clearly define decisions that should be taken before, during and after the occurrence of a disaster. In addition, the risk assessment sheet should outline all possible threats, their nature and severity to the business and should describe the response strategy for each single threat. Security policies should be developed and implemented and users should be trained on security issues with the intention to raise their awareness. Moreover, organizations should hire qualified experts in the area of internet security and also enforce information security frameworks and policies at all levels.

Literature reveals that organisations should take precautions towards their information assets; otherwise they may suffer a wide range of attacks and frauds such as ransomware, phishing, spyware, and malware (Kaimb, 2018). It is also revealed that internet security threats are ever evolving and organisations should

always equip themselves with up to date security tools with the aim to guard against any viruses and intrusions (Honan, 2014). Furthermore, genuine antivirus software and firewalls should be enforced and regular scans should be conducted so that any malware can be detected and be removed immediately before causing any damage to information. Regular backups must be performed in anticipation of any natural or manmade disasters more especially by cyber-attacks.

Summary and conclusion

This paper established that the core need for network security is mainly for: 1. *Protecting business assets*; the prime purpose of network security is to protect valuable assets of an organisation. 2. *Compliance with regulatory requirements*; network security measures ensure that businesses comply with industry regulations about networks and information security standards. 3. *Secured Collaborative working*; network security promotes collaboration amongst workers and the smooth communication between co-worker, clients and suppliers. *Reduced risk*: the adoption and implementation of network security alleviates the impact of security breaches. *Gaining competitive advantage*: developing an effective security system for networks gives organisations and business a competitive edge as clients develop trust towards organisations that have robust security measures.

Internet security is increasingly becoming a great concern for organisations around the world. Businesses have a great responsibility to handle their information assets appropriately, use them strictly for the intended purposes and to not share confidential data with third-party organisations or individuals more especially sensitive information. On the other hand, organisations have the obligation to empower their employees on data protection methods and policies as well as hiring qualified security experts. Most importantly organisations should be aware of how data can be used against them, either by competitors, staff and cyber-criminals. Therefore, organisations should implement robust security measures so as to achieve the safety, security and resilience against cybercrimes.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are provided as the key basic solutions that organisations in Botswana and other countries should implement in order to secure their computers, networks and information systems.

- 1) Educate users: Users should be educated never to open any email attachment in order to avoid the spread of malware.
- 2) Information security policy: Organisations should develop and implement security policies so that everyone in the organisations is aware of their roles with regard to information security.
- 3) Incident response plans: Organisations should develop and implement risk response plans and should know how and when to respond when attacks happen. The management and staff should agree on the plan.
- 4) Organisations should implement access controls, digital signatures and encipherment security mechanisms by the following means:
 - Ensure that all computers are installed with genuine antivirus software.
 - Computer antivirus software must be updated every day to guard against newly created viruses.
 - Ensure that firewalls are properly configured to block viruses and intrusions.
 - Incoming and outgoing mails should be thoroughly filtered to detect viruses in attachments.
 - Ensure that all downloaded files are properly scanned before opening them.
 - Information and documents should be stored in duplicates so as to recover from disasters. It is advisable to backup information in external storage including portable drives and tapes.
 - Network and system logs should be consistently monitored to observe if there are any unusual activities taking place, so that corrective measures are enforced.
- 5) Organisations should have sustainable financial budgets towards internet security.
- 6) Organisations should hire and keep qualified computer systems security experts.

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